

INVESTIGATING THE INTEGRATION OF TRADITIONAL FACE-TO-FACE INSTRUCTION WITH ONLINE LEARNING ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract:

Blended learning, the combination of traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning environments, has gained significant attention in the field of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and English as a Second Language (ESL) education. This article aims to investigate the effectiveness of blended learning models in EFL/ESL contexts and identify optimal combinations of in-person and online interactions. By reviewing relevant studies and examining key components of successful blended learning models, this research sheds light on the potential benefits and challenges associated with implementing blended learning in language education.

Keywords: blended learning, face-to-face instruction, online learning, EFL, ESL, language learning outcomes, learner engagement

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In the ever-evolving landscape of education, the integration of technology has transformed the way students and educators engage with learning. However, as technology continues to advance, educators have been exploring new pedagogical methods to enhance language learning. One such approach that has gained prominence is blended learning, which combines traditional classroom teaching with online learning environments. Donnelly (2010) suggested that blended learning has emerged as a promising educational approach that combines the strengths of face-to-face instruction and online learning platforms.

The integration of online learning platforms with face-to-face instruction can provide students with increased flexibility, personalized learning experiences, and

opportunities for independent practice. Blended learning models can also promote student engagement and motivation by incorporating interactive multimedia resources, collaborative activities, and real-world applications.

Furthermore, studies suggest that the optimal combination of in-person and online interactions depends on various factors, including the learners' proficiency level, learning objectives, and available resources. (Wang, 2010). Moreover, Farrell and Jacobs (2010) proposed that for beginners or students requiring more scaffolding, a higher proportion of face-to-face instruction may be beneficial. However, as learners progress and develop greater autonomy, a higher degree of online interactions can be incorporated to promote self-directed learning and reinforce language skills.

Blended learning provides learners with a diverse range of resources, including multimedia materials, interactive activities, and online language practice platforms. This combination allows learners to reinforce and apply their language skills in different contexts, leading to improved language learning outcomes. Research studies have indicated that blended learning can enhance learners' vocabulary acquisition, reading comprehension, and speaking skills. Furthermore, blended learning offers opportunities for active and interactive learning experiences. Online platforms can incorporate gamification elements, collaborative tasks, and multimedia content, which engage learners and make the learning process more enjoyable. Paolini (2015) stated that the integration of face-to-face instruction with online activities encourages learner participation, interaction, and peer collaboration, fostering a sense of community among learners. Provision of flexibility in terms of time, pace, and location of learning is another benefit of this approach. Learners can access online materials and complete activities at their own convenience, allowing for personalized learning experiences. This flexibility accommodates the diverse learning needs and preferences of EFL/ESL students, enabling them to take ownership of their learning journey.

The flipped classroom model is a popular approach in blended learning,

where students engage with online materials and activities before attending face-to-face sessions. This allows the classroom time to be utilized for interactive discussions, collaborative projects, and individualized support. The flipped classroom model maximizes the benefits of both online and face-to-face interactions, promoting active learning and deeper engagement. Supplementing face-to-face instruction with online activities can provide additional practice opportunities and enhance language skills. Kocoglu, Ozek and Kesli (2011) stated that online platforms can offer interactive exercises, multimedia resources, and virtual simulations, allowing students to practice language concepts and receive immediate feedback. These supplemental activities complement classroom instruction and support learners in consolidating their knowledge. Blended learning projects involve collaborative tasks that require students to work together both online and in person. Students can use online platforms for communication, information sharing, and collaborative document creation. These projects promote critical thinking, problem-solving, and teamwork skills while leveraging the benefits of both face-to-face and online interactions. Osguthorpe, R. T. & Graham, C. R. (2003) suggested that regular evaluation and feedback are crucial for the success of blended learning programs. Educators should design formative assessments that assess both online and face-to-face components, providing insights into students' progress and areas for improvement. Timely feedback helps students gauge their performance and make necessary adjustments to their learning strategies. Effective communication is essential in blended learning environments. Educators should provide clear guidelines regarding expectations, course structure, and the use of online platforms. Kupetz, R. & Ziegenmeyer, B. (2005) proposed that students should be informed about the purpose and benefits of blending learning, as well as the responsibilities and expectations placed on them. Educational institutions should provide adequate support and resources to facilitate student success. This includes access to technical support, online tutorials, and online learning resources. Students should also be provided with guidance on time

management and study skills to navigate the blended learning environment effectively. To ensure effective implementation of blended learning, teachers should receive professional development opportunities. Uğur, Akkoyunlu and Kurbanoglu (2011) stated that training programs should focus on pedagogical strategies for blended learning, effective use of online platforms, and methods for promoting learner engagement. Ongoing support and collaboration among teachers can also facilitate the sharing of best practices and experiences. By combining face-to-face instruction with online learning environments, educators can create a balanced and dynamic learning environment that caters to the diverse needs of language learners.

Reference

1. Donnelly, R. (2010). Harmonizing technology with interaction in blended problem-based learning. *Computers and Education*, 54, 350-359. doi: 10.1016/j.compedu.2009.08.012
2. Farrell, T. S. C. & Jacobs, G. M. (2010). *Essentials for successful English language teaching*. London: Continuum International Publishing Group.
3. Kocoglu, Z., Ozek, Y. & Kesli, Y. (2011). Blended learning: Investigating its potential in an English language teacher training program. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 27, 1124-1134.
4. Kupetz, R. & Ziegenmeyer, B. (2005). Blended learning in a teacher training course: Integrated interactive elearning and contact learning. *ReCALL*, 17, 179-196. doi:10.1017/S095834400500032754
5. Osguthorpe, R. T. & Graham, C. R. (2003). Blended learning environments: Definitions and directions. *The Quarterly Review of Distance Education*, 4, 227-233.
6. Paolini, A. (2015). Enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. *The Journal of Effective Teaching*, 15, 20-33

7. Uğur, B., Akkoyunlu, B. & Kurbanoglu, S. (2011). Students' opinions on blended learning and its implementation in terms of their learning styles. *Education and Information Technologies*, 16, 5-23. doi:10.1007/s10639-009-9109-9

8. Wang, M.-j. (2010). Online collaboration and offline interaction between students using asynchronous tools in blended learning. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 26(6).